

A STUDY ON PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF MATHEMATICS TEACHERS IN HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

Teachers' professional development is now widely regarded as a key determinant of school effectiveness and student achievement. However, Mathematics teachers in higher secondary schools face numerous challenges in their teaching practices, such as a lack of recourse assistance, a lack of innovation teaching policy, and difficulty in using real-life examples in teaching. This study aims to identify Mathematics teachers' professional competence towards higher secondary schools. The sample of 270 mathematics teachers in higher secondary schools was selected from government with private and aided schools located in Vellore district. The data were analyzed using differential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in professional competence of mathematics teachers towards gender, location of school, type of management, Teaching Experience (Years) and marital status of higher secondary school teachers.

Key Words: Teachers, Mathematics, Significance, Statistical Distribution

Introduction:

The professional competencies of Mathematics teachers have sparked a slew of national and international research investigating the skills required to teach various courses at various levels of education (Krauss et al., 2020; Katz and Raths, 1985; Wuttke & Seifried, 2017). This trend has increased the importance of empirical educational research, particularly research used to build courses to improve professional teacher competencies in schools and teacher education (Zakharov et al., 2014).

The main object of the Mathematics Education Program is to encourage students to develop problem-solving abilities with interdisciplinary integration between Mathematics and other subjects, such as Natural Science, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Technology, and Informatics; Mathematics teachers have been requested to provide opportunities for students to experience and use mathematics in practice (Mathematics General Education Program 2018, p. 6). Teachers have always been required in professional development, to have the ability to grasp the program's goals, understand students' thinking, and know how to plan their lessons in the direction of enhancing learners' competencies and abilities in practice. In this context, the Vietnamese Ministry of Education and Training issued a circular on professional standards for teachers, which also sets professional standards and criteria that teachers must achieve.

Enhancing professional skills for Mathematics teachers is one of the important solutions for reducing the issues above in teaching and learning (Schoenfeld, 2011; Silverman & Thompson, 2008). However, few formal programs provide suitable training for aspiring Mathematics instructors in professional competence development, let alone schoolteachers who were overworked in their teaching practice and faced numerous challenges. Within a professional development program for Mathematics teachers, our study explores the process of becoming a Mathematics teacher trainer.

Review of Literature:

Podkhodova, Nataliya; Snegurova, Viktoria; Stefanova, Natalia; Triapitsyna, Alla; Pisareva, Svetlana (2020) The article aims to describe the assessment system of mathematics school teachers' professional competence, which helps identify gaps in their training and design tailor-made retraining courses. 2,359 mathematics teachers from 13 regions of Russia participated in the research on 05-29 September 2017. Finally, the participants conducted video lessons. The results show that the mathematics teachers have difficulties in solving mathematical, teaching, or professional problems so tailor-made retraining courses are required. The developed assessment system underlies designing the courses.

Mastur; Zainuddin (2023) This study aims to determine and examine empirical data related to the influence of teacher professional competence on teacher creativity in elementary schools. This research is a correlational study with sample confidence of 90% or an error rate of 10%, the number of samples obtained was

24 people. Data was taken using 2 methods, namely questionnaires and documentation. This study's results indicate a positive and significant influence between Teacher Professional Competence and Teacher Creativity, with the correlation of the independent variable with the dependent variable being 1.01 at a significance level of 10%. This means that every unit increase in the teacher's professional competence score will simultaneously affect the increase in the teacher's creativity score.

Sample Design:

A sample is a small portion of a selected for observation and analysis of the data. By the process of sampling a relatively small number of individuals, objects or events are selected or analysed in order to find out something about the entire population or universe from which it was selected. For the present study the investigator select 240 mathematics teaches in higher secondary school in Vellore District by the method of Random Sampling.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out if there exists any significant difference between professional competence of mathematics teachers of higher secondary school teachers belonging to the following sub-samples are

- Gender : Male / Female
- Location of School : Rural / Urban
- Type of Management : Government / Govt Aided / Private
- Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10 / 11 -20 / Above 21
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried

Hypotheses of the Study

There is no significant difference between professional competence mathematics teachers of higher secondary school teachers belonging to the following sub-samples are

- Gender : Male / Female
- Location of School : Rural / Urban
- Type of Management : Government / Govt Aided / Private
- Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10 / 11 -20 / Above 21
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried

Tool Used In the Present Study:

Professional Competency Scale:

Dr. Udayagiri Nageshwara Rao, Professor of M.R. College, Vijayanagaram, Andrapradesh (2002) constructed Professional Competencyscale with five points division. The five points are - Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The tool was revalidated for the suitability of our condition.

Scoring Procedure:

In this scale, each response was given a numerical score indicating his/her degree of agreement or disagreement based on five point responses such as Strongly Agree, Agree, undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Score was given to each statement on the basis of positive and negative. The scale has both positive and negative items. For positive statement, the scoring order was 4, 3,0,2,1. And for the negative statement, the scoring order was reversed i.e 1, 2,0,3,4. The maximum score is 160 and minimum will be 0. Many statement used in the scale were suitably changed / modified according to our academic situation.

Differential Analysis:

Table 1: Significance Difference between Gender Mathematics Teachers of Higher Secondary School Teachers in their Professional Competence

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	121	148.71	14.31	0.288	NS
Female	149	148.18	15.25		

It is evident from Table 1 the calculated 't' value is 0.288, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between male and female Mathematics Teachers of higher secondary school teachers with respect to their professional competence.

Table 2: Significance Difference between Locations of School Mathematics Teachers of Higher Secondary School Teachersin their Professional Competence

Location of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	130	149.08	15.18	0.707	NS
Urban	140	147.80	14.49		

It is evident from Table 2 the calculated 't' value is 0.707, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban Mathematics Teachers of higher higher secondary school teachers with respect to their professional competence.

Table 3: Significance Difference between Types of Management Mathematics Teachers of Higher Secondary School Teachers in Their Professional Competence

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	654.332	2	327.166	1.496	NS
Within Groups	58401.534	267	218.732		
Total	59055.867	269			

It is evident from the Table 3 the calculated 'F' value is 1.496, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference Mathematics Teachers sub samples of type of management with respect to their professional competence.

Table 4: Significance Difference between Teaching Experience Mathematics Teachers of Higher Secondary School Teachers in Their Professional Competence

Teaching Experience	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	662.045	2	331.023	1.514	NS
Within Groups	58393.822	267	218.703		
Total	59055.867	269			

It is evident from the Table 4 the calculated 'F' value is 1.514, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference Mathematics Teachers of sub samples of Teaching Experience with respect to their professional competence.

Table 5: Significance Difference between Marital Status Mathematics Teachers of Higher Secondary School Teachers in Their Professional Competence

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Married	138	148.52	15.25	0.121	NS
Unmarried	132	148.31	14.40		

It is evident from Table 5 the calculated 't' value is 0.121, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between married and unmarried Mathematics Teachers of higher secondary school teachers with respect to their professional competence.

Findings of the Study:

- It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between male and female Mathematics Teachers of higher secondary school teachers with respect to their professional competency
- It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban Mathematics Teachers of higher secondary school teachers with respect to their professional competency
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference Mathematics Teachers of of sub samples of type of management with respect to their professional competency
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference Mathematics Teachers of sub samples of Teaching Experience with respect to their professional competency
- It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between married and unmarried Mathematics Teachers of higher secondary school teachers with respect to their professional competency

Conclusion:

The Mathematics teachers' professional competence model plays a critical role in the establishment of materials and organizing the training and fostering workshops for teacher development of mathematical competence. As a result, identifying teacher competency standards or criteria is important in teaching practice to improve professional competence for improving student learning achievement. This study intended to provide frameworks for Mathematics instructors' professional competence in training or fostering and evaluating their practice. The teaching experience of each teacher is enhanced by experimentation; These factors play a crucial part in teaching, since they aid students in gaining a better understanding of subjects. The exchange of the members gave the expression of the real situation, which is a useful point in the products of these groups. The real situations related to linear functions are quite diverse, and the discussion of the members made the expression of the real situation more reasonable, providing a wide range of meaningful and practical scenarios to resolve real-life difficulties.

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